

Factors Guiding Personality Transformation

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ABSTRACT

In this dynamic world, where we witness numerous types of things like news -local, national or international, opinions of people and developments- advancing technology, affect the psyche of an individual due to which human molds his characteristics to camouflage the ambience and inevitably to pace up with present era one has to welcome the amendments in the personality. The persona of a man is the reflection of his thoughts and deeds. Every individual has his own charm as a personality. The behavior of a person never switches with a blink of an eye, it transforms gradually with the impact of an ambience, biological factors and a company of people he is surrounded with for the considerable time span. It is his character which guides other in making decision if they want to be in his acquaintances or not. Moreover, the traits decide the success and the failure of a man. The character of a man spearheads his life towards success. There are many arrays which contribute in building up distinguished personality. In the following paragraph, I will be discussing multitude like NEWS, developments, ambience, peers and society explaining the importance in everyone's life in terms to be on front line at social end.

Key words: -Geographical influence, newscast, advancing technology, social activities, friends.

Introduction

NEWS→Developments→Ambience→Peers→Society

To commence the description of the above-mentioned factors: NEWS, development, ambience, peers and society lets first understand the term 'Personality'. Every individual qualifies to be distinguished from others due to various traits in him. All such figurative characteristics in a man help in identifying us if we want to be in an association with him or not. We humans call us social animals and to be socialized we need to build up acquaintances - formal or informal. Most of us have huge list of friends on social network sites, in our mobile contact list but the strength

of cord of relationship decides our behavior. It has become forlorn trends to have quantitative list of friends not qualitative. The substantial thing to understand is that there is instability in the relationship due to variation in behaviors and the behavior of man is influenced from surroundings, friends and the society where he lives in.

Initially, lets understand how atmosphere affects the character of a person. The geographical variation tied up with climate of a region which plays crucial role in building up behavior of a person. Even the surveys have been conducted by various bodies summarizing the fact that places witnessing temperature around 22 degrees Celsius are more relaxed and happier in comparison to the people from region experiencing climatic temperature above or less than 22 degree Celsius. Weather conditions truly operates the mood of a humans. These relationships between temperature clemency and personality factors were replicated in a larger dataset of 12,499 ZIP-code level locations (the lowest geographical level feasible) in the United States ($N=1,660,638$) Scorching heat and humid weather become so unpleasant and make us uncomfortable to focus on work resulting in agitated behavior or high temperament which may cause clashes in the personality and adversely affecting the relationship.[1] The team of authors Wei et al., conducted a survey and reach to the conclusion that factors like amiableness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability and personal growth and plasticity (extraversion and openness to experience) go with the climatic conditions of the region. Even it has been observed that many entrepreneurs focus on the interior of the offices to provide at least all basic amenities to the employees to have their entire attention or focus on work only. The ambience of the offices is furnished with every lavish fitting ensuring drastically opposite environment in four walls from the geographical factors, giving successful assurance of retention of the employees because staff find the environment pleasurable and friendly to work in. Now you must be wondering thathow the interior of a place affects the traits of a person. It happens because we all are working to earn livelihood and then further to have the splendid life. So, it is being to be fortunate to have all the basic facilities in a lavish form through the company perks without any economical investment and nobody wants to lose such bountiful lifestyle and to ensure this the attitude, dealing and even the conduct of a staff varies a lot. The person becomes manipulator with his characteristics because he wants please every person associated with him at work place. [2] As per the studies made by Rentfrow, show how aspects of the social and physical

environment affect and correlate with various indices as health and morbidity, well-being, crime rates, identity, creativity, and community orientation. The good behavior of an employee helps him to have innovative ideas. This further encourages the productivity of a company. It has been seen that the person having many clashes with others is not liked by others so in this way he loses his personal contact, but it is not easy for a human to live alone. Everybody needs at least one shoulder where he can rely without any hesitation, ill feelings, deception and manipulation. For the quality friend list no matters the list has one or more count one ought to mold himself according the company of a person because it will help in creating a conflict free environment, providing ease to each other.

Further moving to another component that is NEWS, the full form of NEWS is North, East West and south that means leaving none of the directions, dimensions of the geographical sphere uncovered. Due to globalization the world is shrinking that means every corner of the earth has become accessible. We are aware with the happenings of every region no matter it is near or far. Availability of various media sources have aided the approachability. In the morning we wake up with a gadget in our hands having numerous notifications on it. Some of the notifications are authentic, some are factual, some are sarcastic, and some are witty. Some news is latest which get viral in form of short videos which are made LIVE from ground zero and forwarded on social network sources like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Messenger, Twitter and many more. We go through such notifications and messages which leave a direct or an indirect impact on the psyche of a human. [3] In the opinion of Szabo and Hopkinson, the newscast is the root cause of attention-diverting and interrupts the progressive relaxation. The cognitive functioning is now out of the control of a human, it is more influenced by the things he watches and gets operated accordingly. This causes the severe mood swings among people these days who are more engrossed into gadgets. Though witnessing mood swings and variation in a personality are the symptoms of being normal human being because a man undergoes numerous situations in a life span and he behaves accordingly. But the alarming thing is that a man is expressing drastic mood swings and has become victim of many psychological issues and by which even the man himself is not aware and is badly trapped into such fatal and chronic issues. Some people are in habit of reading newspapers and it has been observed that newspapers highlight the unusual, least important or the news of accidents, social evils like rape cases, murders, suicides with more extra ordinary factors which has scared people a lot they feel unsafe and unsecured while stepping out

of the homes. No doubt we need awareness about the happenings of the society through such sources, but the interpretation of the incidents matters a lot, it can be done with the optimistic perspective that means discussing the incidents with its way outs. Example if we talk about murder cases, such coverage of news shall come up with the knowledge of helplines and the punishments associated with such cases so that it gives awareness to the people in the society with the rights. The acknowledgment about the rights and the facilitations provided by the government to its citizens ensures the sense of being secure in the nation. This further helps man to live carefree and more relaxed and even the evil bodies will stop indulging in such criminal acts because with such impactful NEWS the system will also work more efficiently. Talking about another type of NEWS like suicide, such NEWS has escalated the count of such cases because many people have common problems in their own lives and when they come across reports in newspaper that some person has committed suicide due to so and so reason. The reader starts to co-relate his life with that tragic case of suicide and he feels that suicide is the only remedy to get rid of that situation. How powerful the NEWS becomes at that moment and it influences the psyche of a reader in such a way that he gets entirely trapped into the web of NEWS and becomes the victim of his own murder- suicide. The matter of concern is that such NEWS is equally important to published and broadcasted but again the point is same that the framing of these reports can be informative for many such psychological patients who don't accept themselves as patients. Such reports are very sensitive and are to be dealt with smartness. These types of NEWS shall have some information about the rehab centers, conveying people that it's quite normal to have visits to such centers and even the meetings with psychiatrists. Even the reasons behind suicide can be discussed with the possible solutions. Such situations lead to excess stress and even depression, in this way person will not have productivity, efficiency and quality in his work putting adverse effects on the growth of the mindset, body of the person and even on the development of the nation. On the other hand, if we say newscast helps in controlling the emotions of a person too. A man gratifies his anger emotions by watching violence on mass media [4] This amazing concept is interpreted as a Catharsis Theory which is discussed by Douglas A. that doing something to "vent" aggression as a method of reducing aggressive feelings and behaviors, acts like a valve and the pressure gets released by watching media violence or playing violent video games, continues to enjoy widespread public support despite a lack of empirical support. It gives sense of satisfaction by watching contended verdicts

on the cases which become a global issue. He finds himself as one of the characters of the story or news and takes pleasure by becoming part of that aggressive act and eases him to overcome the anger, agitation which feels in his factual world.

Next, the advancing technology has also severe impact on the character of the human being because in this techno savvy epoch numerous advance equipment have come into our lives making the tasks easy and resulting luxurious lifestyle. Advancing technology has given us comfort in every sphere and it has increased the efficiency of doing work. A very common phrase 'Necessity is the mother of all the inventions' has proven the power of its meaning because world has advanced in a lot, At present if we say that human has developed or invented wide range of products to facilitate his life in terms of livelihood, appliances, transportation, medication and many more other fields and even we have got range of varieties in those products. We all are aware with this that everything comes with pros and cons. When we say that technology has made every person, place accessible but at the same time we cannot deny that it has isolated a man from another man sitting next to him. It has been observed that people isolate themselves from the real world and please themselves with the gadgets, social network sites. People prefer playing games on computers and sitting under air-conditioned roof. They have forgotten the laborious work that means almost 0% physical work causing so many fatal diseases and harmonically imbalances.[5] Aboujaoude tells in his article that the technology embraces many pros and cons and it has the tendency to devastate the cognitive functions of a person The task is more psychological exercises giving unwanted stress all the time. People talk to other people on distance to whom they even do not know and they have nothing to do with their lives though multimedia sources, but they have no time for their family. These days family is living under one roof, but members have very formal interaction with each other. The perceived ease to use technology and intention to use changes with time. [6] Behrenbruch et al, found that two personality traits varies the synchronization between perceived ease of use and intention to use with the passage of time and also due to other factors influencing the mindset of a person. People come across number of other people on social media and people behave with each other without any favourable consent and they even don't care about the feelings of other or even they play emotional games. They switch to additional personality behaviour, people do not hesitate to invade the privacy of others. We have become sadistic these days, we peep into other's lives by ensuring the next level relationship goals with partners but hiding our main motive of invasion

because we have become sadistic. Intentionally or unintentionally we are involved because it gives pleasure to us. It has become most common way to overcome own frustration by looking at more sad people than oneself. People have made it as a source of entertainment for themselves. How manipulator they have become with their own conscious. Inevitably it has become vicious circle in our lives to drag each other by wearing fake mask of smile on their faces

Social Penetration Theory also gives idea more vividly, more you disclose more you are on risk of getting exploited. People please you by wearing multiple masks and they are good at hiding their real picture. When the cost of penetration over weighs the benefits then it becomes **de-penetration**. The cruel plays of deception and hiding real personality and behavior can even cost the lives of many. The victim when acknowledges the wrong consent of a man (may be as friend, fiancé, husband, brother, sister, aunt etcetera) then he gets badly hurt sometimes ends up with extreme step in terms of murder or even a suicide. The short-term benefits of having pleasure has made human to adopt multiple faces. [7] Dr. Panos explained the mechanism of the intrapersonal and interpersonal behavior of an individual with the effect of Social penetration Theory in terms of online communication and offline communication (face to face). It explains how personal information is negotiated and presented in society and it initiates with the self-disclosure. Self-disclosure has a central role in social penetration. Being in touch with society sometimes lead to mundane conversation also. It is encountered by maximum people through digital personal network sources.

Moving ahead, the next factor which I will discuss in detail is peer. The behavior of the person is also decided by his company. If a person is in office and among colleagues and boss he will be formal with his body language, speaking, dress and everything from head to toe(hair dos, gestures, attires and footwear) he need to mind his language and business. Whereas when a person is in the company of friends he is carefree bird who can do things of his choice, there one can do anything of his choice, he will not be formal in language. One feels more relaxed and comfortable with friends and comes up as real personality with no filters in the act. Being with friend is a warm feeling. [8] *M. J. Connor says Children are more vulnerable and they get more adversely affected by the peers because they have a fear of not being accepted. We observe our peer very keenly because spend quality time with friends. Friend in need is friend indeed even good friends' company brings a positive change in another friend. To accompany his friend, he

even changes his deeds or personality in order to provide company to the friend. Such supportive factor teaches the exclusive ingredients of the life like cooperation, understanding, and caring etcetera. And of course, company of a man matters a lot, it decides the next change in him. If a man is fortunate to have a good companion then he is going to outshine in the world with joy and happiness but unfortunately, if he is not in a good friend circle then there could be possibility of his drowning. Bad friends can even drag him in the bad habits. But the influence of a good friend or a bad friend is decided by the determination of a person. How much he is determined and obsessed by his traits. The spontaneous switching of a characteristics is rare whereas there is always seen that the gradual change is more sustainable.

Last but not the least, society too plays an indispensable role in commanding the personality of a person. Society is the domain from where a human can never escape otherwise he will not be a social animal anymore. Opting to be in isolation is extreme unusual personality transformation. So, willingly or unwillingly we must be part of it. Now the point is that in a society we have range of people with various mindsets and people from different backgrounds and generation. If we will not function accordingly then we will become hot potato. Coming up in limelight is the call of a man because it is the man who gives chance to others to speak or comment or to compliment. The point is that it is not wrong to follow the heart but what if you are going odd and becoming rebels but on the contrary you don't have the courage to accept the criticism. So, it is always better to follow that which you can bear and accept otherwise in an influence of any other personality you have changed yourself, but you don't have that much courage to carry it or to team it with your present personality undoubtedly you will become matter of discussion or even may be matter of laughter. It is all in our hands that whether we want to be odd one or the common. Also, we need to change ourselves with the flow of time looking into the latest trends of cuisines, attires, interiors etcetera

Hammering the last nail, it can be concluded that every individual is a combination of different ingredients of behavior and traits and with such unique combination everyone is distinguished from every other person. Many have tendency to bring change in themselves and such feature of being flexible make the **survival of the fittest**. It is truly well said that the tree bearing fruits always bend whereas adamant people will stand stiff like tall trees which will be easily targeted by the tycoons. Keeping in mind that such adaptability shall bring harm neither to oneself nor to

the society. Moreover, nobody can achieve cent percent perfection but the attitude to have amendments on time and understanding the need of the time makes the person to step on the top of the victory box.

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